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Inflammatory Bowel Disease

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Introduction

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) can be described as chronic inflammatory condition associated more commonly with small intestine rather than large intestine. It is rarely ulcerative and not a multisystemic disease. The condition is characterized by vomiting, diarrhoea, changes in the appetite and weight loss. Being a chronic inflammation, it is predisposed with several factors like immune dysregulation, environmental factors, mechanical factors, chemical factors, oxidative stress and angiogenesis, which leads to altered gene expression thus leading to altered gut microbiome which alters the absorption, motility, structural and functional disruption which further leads to clinical manifestation. Breed and geographical predisposition are also observed with IBD.

Inflammatory bowel disease is a chronic gastric disease which includes chronic enteropathy, food responsive enteropathy, antibiotic responsive enteropathy, steroid responsive enteropathy and infectious enteropathy. The chronic large bowel diseases which are not exactly an enteropathy include infectious colitis (histiocytic ulcerative colitis or granulomatous colitis), food responsive diarrhoea (FRD), antibiotic-responsive diarrhoea (ARD) and stress colitis. Chronic gastro-intestinal signs can also be caused by neoplasm, parasitism and lymphangiectasia.

The extra intestinal diseases that mimic the IBD are endocrine diseases like Addison's disease and hyperthyroidism, uremia, toxicity, hepatobiliary disease, pancreatic diseases like pancreatic insufficiency and pancreatitis, paraneoplastic conditions.

Common types of IBD

1. Steroid responsive enteropathy:

It is an idiopathic inflammatory bowel disease which include compatible clinical history, chronic signs, histopathologic findings, exclusion of the mimics, lack of response to therapeutics other than glucocorticoids.

It depends on the two factors,

- Reactivity of the immune system to self, due to the upregulation of the innate immunity.
- Alteration in the pattern recognition receptor expression, proliferation of lymphocytes and its altered regulation.

2. Food responsive enteropathy:

It accounts for 50-60% of the total IBD cases. Many dietary factors affect the gut health like, antigen, fiber content, fat content, digestibility, impact on the commensals and alteration in the consistency of food. Common diagnostic and therapeutic food trials include highly digestible diet, hydrolysed diet and high fiber diet. Food elimination trial exclusively accounts for 2 to 4 weeks which evaluates immunologic and non-immunologic sensitivities.

3. Infectious enteropathy:

It includes the agents like fungi, viruses, parasites and bacteria.

- **Fungi:** Histoplasmosis, Cryptococcosis, Zygomycetes
- **Algae:** Protothecosis
- **Virus:** Canine parvo virus, feline panleukopenia, canine distemper, corona virus, circo virus, rota virus. Rarely feline infectious peritonitis, feline leukemia virus. Poorly described canine viruses: sapo virus, astro virus. Poorly described feline viruses: novel parvo virus (boca parvo virus and proto parvovirus), astro virus, adeno virus
- **Parasites:** Round worms (*Toxocara canis*, *Toxocara cati*, *Toxocara leonina*, *Trichuris vulpis*, Hook worms (*Ancylostoma caninum*, *Ancylostoma tubaeforme*), *Echinococcus multilocularis*, Diphyliidium, Taenia.
- **Protozoa:** Giardia, cryptosporidium, *Tritrichomonas foetus*, *Pentatrichomonas hominis*
- **Bacteria:** Salmonella, Clostridium, Camphylobacter, *Clostridium difficile*, *Brachyspira pilosicoli*

Role of bacteria in maintaining gut health

Protect against intestinal pathogens, provision of nutrients, improvement in barrier function, stimulation of intestinal development, modulation of immune system, facilitate nutrient digestion and absorption.

Bacterial metabolites:

- Short chain fatty acids: acetate, propionate, butyrate. They provide energy to colonic epithelium, regulate energy metabolism and have an anti-inflammatory effect.
- Secondary bile acids: they have metabolic and immunomodulatory properties.
- Tryptophan metabolites: alters serotonin level and regulates mucosal permeability.

4. Antibiotic responsive enteropathy:

It is also called as tylosin responsive diarrhoea and small intestinal dysbiosis. The biomarkers of gastrointestinal health and function include fusobacterium, faecobacterium, blantia, *Clostridium hiranonis*. In dysbiosis, there will be abundance of *E. coli* in the intestinal microflora.

Diagnosis

Clinical history, faecal examination, serological examination, tests for infectious agents, complete blood count and cortisol levels provide significant insight into the disease process. Gastrointestinal absorption can be determined by parameters like cobalamine and folate levels, trypsin like immune reactivity and pancreatic lipase like immunoreactivity. Faecal calprotectin (S100A8/A9 protein complex) has been also found to be of diagnostic importance in patients with IBD. Diagnostic imaging studies such as ultrasonography (USG), radiography, computed tomography and contrast USG are also used for evaluation of intestinal morphology. Other diagnostic tests include endoscopy, surgical evaluation, study of motility and histopathology.

Treatment

Treatment for inflammatory bowel disease includes but, not limited to dietary trials, microbial manipulation, anti-inflammatory medications, immunosuppressive medications, symptomatic medication including anti-nausea and appetite stimulants, supplements like cobalamine and folate.

- Goals of therapy are to restore function of gut barrier, shut down the inflammation, resolve clinical signs and minimize the side effect of medication.

Anti-inflammatory medications include,

- Immunosuppressive agents: cyclosporine and azathioprine
- Chemotherapeutic medication: Clorambucil
- Non-steroidal therapy: sulfasalazine

Future consideration includes stem cell therapy and low dose radiation therapy, but needs much validation before including in clinical practices.

For the success of the therapy there should be synergism between

- Dietary management which includes diet with optimum fiber content, fat content and carbohydrate content which maintains the microbiota.
- Anti-inflammatory therapy including steroid or non-steroidal drugs which reduces the inflammation.
- Microbiome manipulation using antibiotics, faecal microbiota transfer, prebiotics and probiotics. The probiotics increase the short chain fatty acids, improve gut barrier, modulate immune function, improves host defence protein generation. Prebiotic include yeast and derivatives of fructose oligosaccharides. Faecal microbiota transfer is mainly used in bacterial IBD due to clostridium difficile infection.

Therapies to target in future:

- Specific cytokines: TNF alpha, interleukin 12 and 23
- White blood trafficking: integrin alpha 4 beta 7
- Restoring gut barrier: zonulin
- Optimizing gut microbiota: targeted probiotics, maximizing prebiotic supplements

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